

noDice: Inference for Probabilistic Programs with Nondeterminism and Conditioning - Artifact Overview

Artefact Overview for the noDice Probabilistic Programming Language

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1 INTRODUCTION

The artifact contains the implementation of noDice, a probabilistic inference engine which supports both Bayesian conditioning and nondeterminism. The purpose of the tool is to infer the maximum conditional probability that a given probabilistic program with nondeterminism returns a value. The artifact contains the source code of the tool, but we also provide a Docker image to easily run and evaluate the artifact.

1.1 Supported Claims

The artifact is meant to support all claims from Section 6 of the corresponding paper, where the relevant claims are based on the performance of noDice on several benchmarks as shown in Table 1 of the original paper. All relevant benchmarks are included in the artifact, and the evaluation of these benchmarks can be reproduced to support the following claims:

- (1) noDice with state compression scales similarly to Dice for purely probabilistic programs
- (2) The effect of nondeterminism on the performance of noDice is negligible
- (3) Model checking is a not significant part of the runtime for noDice
- (4) State compression heavily reduces the size of MDP
- (5) noDice outperforms Storm on some of the benchmarks

The claims listed above are supported by the artifact as follows:

- (1) The claim follows from the performance of Dice and noDice on the couponProb and Bayesian network benchmarks.
- (2) The claim follows from the performance of noDice on the 3sat benchmarks, where the runtime remains largely unchanged as the amount of nondeterminism increases.
- (3) The claim follows from the performance of noDice on the nondeterministic benchmarks, i.e. runway, couponNdet, network and 3sat.
- (4) This claim holds for any benchmark, and can be tested by running noDice on any benchmark with and without state compression to compare the results.
- (5) This claim is supported by comparing the runtime of Storm and noDice on the benchmarks, which should behave similarly to Table 1 from the main submission.

2 HARDWARE DEPENDANCIES

In order to run the Docker image a Docker installation is required. The Docker image itself is \approx 12 GB in size and is build for arm64 architecture, and we recommend running the artifact on a machine with arm64 architecture.

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The Docker image for the artefact has been tested by the authors on a fresh machine with ARM macOS and an M3 pro chip with 36 GB of RAM.

3 GETTING STARTED GUIDE

We will now outline how to set up the docker image and run noDice on a simple benchmark. Docker itself can be installed by following the instructions at: <https://docs.docker.com/get-started/get-docker/>. Afterwards, you can pull the Docker image for the artifact with the following command:

```
docker pull tguertler/nodice:00PSLA_2026
```

You can now load the image and start an interactive Docker container based on it by entering the following command:

```
docker run -it tguertler/nodice:00PSLA_2026
```

You can stop the container at any time by entering the command `exit`. For now, we will run some simple experiments to verify that the container is running correctly.

3.1 Testing a Small Benchmark

You can run noDice on a small benchmark by entering the following command in the container:

```
dune exec -- nodice benchmarks/nodice/runway/runway3.dice
```

Here, `benchmarks/nodice/runway/runway3.dice` is the path to the benchmark file in the docker container. The program should terminate almost instantly and print something similar to the following output on the command line:

```
opam@6602e38e763b:/noDice/nodice$ dune exec -- nodice benchmarks/nodice/runway/
runway3.dice
===== [ Maximum Probabilities (noDice) ] =====
Value Probability
true  0.036095
false 0.988030

===== [ Runtimes ] =====
Task          Time (seconds)
Compilation   0.004189
Model Checking 0.000491
noDice (total) 0.004680

===== [ BDD, ADD and MDP sizes ] =====
BDD nodes    62
ADD nodes    70
MDP states   16
```

3.2 Testing a Simple Script

The artifact also provides simple scripts to run full classes of benchmarks at once. One such script is `baselines.sh`, which we will now execute. Notably, the script must be run from its parent directory `nodice`, which is also the directory where the docker container starts by default. Hence we can execute the script with the following command:

```
scripts/baselines.sh
```

The script should terminate after a couple seconds and print quite a bit of output to the command line. For comparison, a sample output can be found in the file `baselines_out.txt` which is included in the `scripts/sampleOutputs` folder of the artifact.

4 STEP BY STEP GUIDE

The experiments from the original paper are based on the performance of the artifact on several benchmarks. We will now present a guide to recreate the performance results from Table 1 in the original paper by running those benchmarks.

4.1 Running Benchmarks with Scripts

We provide simple scripts which evaluate a full class of benchmarks. Scripts can be found in the `scripts` folder when starting the Docker container, and we provide two scripts per benchmark class, one to evaluate the benchmarks with state compression, and one without state compression. Here, the script running noDice without state compression will have the additional suffix `"_u"`, i.e. for the *Runway* benchmarks we have the scripts `runway.sh` and `runway_u.sh`, both of which will have almost identical runtimes. We also provide scripts to run Storm on all benchmark classes, which will have the suffix `"_s"`. Below we list the scripts for each benchmark class and the time they roughly should be expected to take. A script causes a time out if any benchmark takes more than 20 minutes to terminate.

Class	noDice		Storm	
Runway	<code>runway.sh</code>	$< 1 \text{ min}$	<code>runway_s.sh</code>	$< 1 \text{ min}$
CouponProb	<code>couponProb.sh</code>	$\approx 3 \text{ min}$	<code>couponProb_s.sh</code>	$\approx 15 \text{ min}$
CouponNdet	<code>couponNdet.sh</code>	$\approx 1 \text{ min}$	<code>couponNdet_s.sh</code>	$\approx 1 \text{ min}$
Network	<code>network.sh</code>	$\approx 3 \text{ min}$	<code>network_s.sh</code>	$< 1 \text{ min}$
Fair Exchange	<code>rabin.sh</code>	$\approx 5 \text{ min}$	<code>rabin_s.sh</code>	$< 1 \text{ min}$
Bayesian	<code>bayesian.sh</code>	$\approx 4 \text{ min}$	<code>bayesian_s.sh</code>	$\approx 1 \text{ min}$
BayesianNdet	<code>bayesianNdet.sh</code>	$\approx 4 \text{ min}$	<code>bayesianNdet_s.sh</code>	$\approx 1 \text{ min}$
3sat	<code>3sat.sh</code>	$\approx 2 \text{ min}$	<code>3sat_s.sh</code>	Timeout

The times listed above are based on running noDice and Storm natively, execution in a Docker container may take longer. Scripts must be run from the `nodice` folder where the Docker container starts by default, and not the `scripts` folder. We can thus run `couponProb.sh` using the command

```
scripts/couponProb.sh
```

Sample outputs for each script can be found in the `scripts/sampleOutputs` folder of the artifact.

4.2 Interpreting Outputs – noDice

The scripts print the performance metrics for each benchmark program directly onto the command line. We will now explain how to relate this command line output to the values in Table 1 of the paper. As an example, consider the following output for the *Runway-30* benchmark:

```

===== [ Runway-30 ] =====
===== [ Maximum Probabilities (noDice) ] =====
Value   Probability
true    0.005902405618
false   0.9997622739

===== [ Runtimes ] =====
Task           Time (seconds)
Compilation    0.764747
Model Checking 0.223656
noDice (total) 0.988403

===== [ BDD, ADD and MDP sizes ] =====
BDD nodes     12507
ADD nodes     13026
MDP states    1048

```

Here, `Runway-30` at the top describes the name of the Benchmark as found in Table 1. Below that, we find the maximum probability to return each value. Note that these values are not found in the tables, and they do not need to sum to 1 if the program contains nondeterminism.

Further below, we find the runtime statistics of the benchmark: The rows `Compilation` and `Model Checking` state the time taken for the inference part, and the times correspond the respective table columns with the same name. `noDice (total)` states the total runtime of the `noDice` algorithm. This total time corresponds to either the `noDice` column if the algorithm was run *with* state compression, or to the `noDiceu` column if the algorithm was run *without* state compression.

Below that we find statistics regarding the sizes of BDD, ADD or MDP sizes. These numbers correspond directly to the similarly named columns in the tables. Notably, Table 1 only lists MDPs sizes for `noDice` with state compression. The uncompressed MDP sizes are not reported in the tables of the original paper.

Note that for probabilistic benchmarks, the output will additionally list the total runtime of `Dice` below the runtime of `noDice`. This number directly corresponds to the `Dice` column in Table 1. The output will also include the probabilities calculated by `Dice`, but these values are not in the tables.

4.3 Using Individual Benchmarks or New Inputs

It is possible to test individual benchmarks by using the following command in the `nodice` folder:

```
dune exec -- nodice path/to/benchmark [optional arguments]
```

Here, `path/to/benchmark` refers to the path to the benchmark we want to perform inference on, where the file structure of the benchmarks from the experiments is described in [Section 6](#). `noDice` supports two optional arguments:

```

--dice    Additionally run Dice alongside noDice
--uncompressed  Run noDice without state compression

```

Thus, we can test the `Runway-30` benchmark without state compression with the command:

```
dune exec -- nodice benchmarks/nodice/runway/runway30.dice --uncompressed
```

The Docker image also allows us to test `noDice` on inputs which are not included in the artifact already. To do so, assume we want to share a local file `subOpt.dice` from a local sub-directory `local/folder` of the current directory with the Docker container. We can run the image with file sharing enabled using the following command:

```
docker run -it -v ./local/folder:/noDice/nodice/data tguertler/nodice:OOPSLA_2025
```

This allows us to access the local/folder directory within the Docker container via the data directory, and we can run noDice on files from this shared directory as follows:

```
dune exec -- nodice data/subOpt.dice
```

For an overview of the syntax and semantics of noDice we refer to the README.md file of the artifact.

4.4 Interpreting Outputs – Storm

In the main paper, we compare the performance of noDice with the performance of the probabilistic model checker Storm¹. Storm is included in the Docker container of the artifact, and all benchmarks from Table 1 can be tested with Storm for comparison. We will now outline how the command line output of Storm can be interpreted, as seen again with the example of the Runway-30 benchmark:

```
=====[ Runway-30 ]=====
Storm 1.11.1

Date: Fri Feb 20 12:46:28 2026
Command line arguments: --prism benchmarks/storm/runway/runway30.nm --prop
  benchmarks/storm/runway/properties.txt --conditional bisection
Current working directory: /noDice/nodice

Time for model input parsing: 0.001s.

Time for model construction: 0.552s.

-----
Model type:   MDP (sparse)
States:      328739
Transitions: 1937708
Choices:     376180
Reward Models: none
State Labels: 5 labels
* deadlock -> 1800 item(s)
* init -> 1 item(s)
* win -> 1728 item(s)
* fail -> 432 item(s)
* acc -> 360 item(s)
Choice Labels: none
-----

Model checking property "success": Pmax=? [(F (win)) || (F (acc))] ...
Result (for initial states): 0.005907686427
Time for model checking: 0.718s.

Model checking property "failure": Pmax=? [(F (fail)) || (F (acc))] ...
Result (for initial states): 0.999815464
Time for model checking: 0.588s.
```

Here, the probability for the program to return true is encoded by the "success" property, and Storm determines this probability to be 0.005907686427. Similarly, the "failure" property describes the probability for the program to return false, which Storm determines to be 0.999815464.

¹<https://www.stormchecker.org>

These property names are consistent for all boolean benchmarks, i.e. the probability for "success" always corresponds to the probability for the respective noDice program to return true.

Finally, the reported MDP size from Table 1 of the main paper can be retrieved from the middle of the output, namely the number of states, which in this example is 328739. As for runtime, the "Storm" column Table 1 of the main paper reports the total time needed for Storm. This time is calculated as the sum of the time for model input parsing, model construction as well as all model checking queries. In the example above, this would sum to 1.859 seconds.

5 REUSABILITY GUIDE

We will now present the two key components of the artifact which may need to be modified to adapt the artifact to new use cases. We acknowledge that adapting the artifact to new use cases will often require changing the source code, which we consider to be the most notable limitation of it. Afterwards, we briefly comment on running the artifact with new inputs.

5.1 Inference.ml

This file is the most important part of the artifact, as it contains the functions which coordinate the inference process as a whole. In particular, the function `infer` takes the string of a noDice program as input and calls the necessary functions to perform parsing, compilation, ADD construction and model checking. Currently, the function simply prints the output of the inference process to the command line, but the function code can be modified to suit use cases which require other outputs.

We also want to highlight the `evaluate_add` function, which coordinates the ADD evaluation. In particular, `evaluate_add` calls the `Add.bisection_float` function with the given ADD, which in turn performs model checking. The arguments of the function can be set to perform state compression or use exact arithmetic instead of floating point numbers.

5.2 Add.ml

This file contains most operations which concern ADDs and MDPs. Most notable here are the `apply_guard` function, which takes two BDDs and constructs the corresponding ADD, and the `compress_ADD` function which performs state compression. Additionally, the file also contains the `bisection_float` function, which possibly compresses the ADD and performs model checking with the bisection-based algorithm.

Beyond that, the file also includes the function `add_to_jani_file_compressed` as well as `add_to_prism_file_compressed` to write the lifted MDP after state compression into a file in the respective format. These functions can be used to retrieve the compiled MDP and use it outside of the noDice inference algorithm.

5.3 Writing New noDice Programs

The artifact can be used to perform inference on any given noDice program, and is not limited to benchmark programs which are already included in the artifact. For an overview of the syntax and semantics of noDice we refer to the `README.md` file of the artifact. A description of how to run the artifact on a given benchmark is presented in [Section 4.3](#)

6 COMPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: FILE STRUCTURE OF BENCHMARKS

We will briefly outline the file structure of the benchmarks directory, which contains the benchmark files used in the experiments. Below, we will show an overview of the benchmark directory.

```

nodice/benchmarks/
|-- baselines
|   |-- alarm.dice
|   |-- digitRecognition.dice
|   |-- evidence1.dice
|   |-- evidence2.dice
|   |-- murderMystery.dice
|   |-- noisyOr.dice
|   |-- twocoins.dice
|-- nodice
|   |-- 3sat
|       |-- 3sat-0.dice
|       |-- ...
|       |-- 3sat-100.dice
|   |-- bayesian
|       |-- survey.dice
|       |-- hepar2.dice
|       |-- insurance.dice
|       |-- water.dice
|       |-- alarm.dice
|       |-- survey_ndet.dice
|       |-- hepar2_ndet.dice
|       |-- insurance_ndet.dice
|       |-- water_ndet.dice
|       |-- alarm_ndet.dice
|   |-- coupon
|       |-- coupon2-5-ndet.dice
|       |-- ...
|       |-- coupon2-10-ndet.dice
|       |-- coupon2-5-obs.dice
|       |-- ...
|       |-- coupon2-14-obs.dice
|   |-- diamond
|       |-- diamond-100.dice
|       |-- ...
|       |-- diamond-10000.dice
|   |-- rabin
|       |-- rabin10.dice
|       |-- ...
|       |-- rabin500.dice
|-- runway
|   |-- runway3.dice
|   |-- ...
|   |-- runway60.dice

```

Note that we did not enumerate all files in the directories, but instead we present the naming scheme for the remaining files below:

Class	Directory	Benchmark	Values
CouponProb	benchmarks/nodice/coupon/	coupon2-i-obs.dice	$i \in \{5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14\}$
Runway	benchmarks/nodice/runway/	runwayi.dice	$i \in \{3, 7, 15, 40, 41, 45, 60\}$
CouponNdet	benchmarks/nodice/coupon/	coupon2-i-ndet.dice	$i \in \{5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10\}$
Network	benchmarks/nodice/diamond/	diamond-i.dice	$i \in \{100, 200, 300, 400, 500, 1000, 2000, 4000, 6000, 8000, 10000\}$
3sat	benchmarks/nodice/3sat/	3sat-i.dice	$i \in \{0, 25, 50, 75, 100\}$
Fair Exchange	benchmarks/nodice/rabin/	rabini.dice	$i \in \{10, 50, 100, 250, 500\}$

We can construct a valid path to a benchmark by instantiating i with one of the possible values, and combining the directory and benchmark name. For example, the CouponProb benchmark for $i = 8$ will be called coupon2-8-obs.dice and is in benchmarks/nodice/coupon/coupon2-8-obs.dice. We can run this benchmark with the following command:

```
dune exec -- nodice benchmarks/nodice/coupon/coupon2-8-obs.dice
```